

Impact of Leptin and Thyroid Hormone on Obesity in Wasit Province, Iraq

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Abstract:

The current study investigates the correlation between thyroid dysfunction, specifically thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) levels, and obesity in children and adolescents. The researchers also assessed the levels of leptin hormone and lipid profiles in obese individuals compared to non-obese individuals."

The study included 100 participants aged 7 to 15 years, divided into two groups: 50 obese individuals and 50 non-obese individuals as a control group. The body mass index (BMI) was used to determine obesity. Blood samples were collected from both groups to measure various parameters, including serum leptin, TSH, total cholesterol, triacylglycerol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL), and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL).

The statistical analysis of the data, performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), revealed significant differences between the two groups. The obese group showed a significant increase ($p < 0.01$) in serum leptin levels compared to the non-obese group. In contrast, the non-obese group had higher levels of T4, T3, and TSH, along with lower levels of leptin and all lipid profiles. The obese group had lower levels of T3 and T4, higher levels of TSH, and lower levels of leptin, as well as significant differences in lipid profiles when compared to the non-obese group.

These findings suggest that there is a relationship between thyroid dysfunction, leptin hormone levels, and lipid profiles in obese children and adolescents. However, it's important to note that the specific mechanisms underlying this relationship and the direction of causality are not discussed in the provided information. Further research would be needed to explore the implications and potential therapeutic interventions related to these findings.

Keywords: TSH level, thyroid dysfunction, children obesity, body mass index.

Introduction

It is known that obesity has several effects, some of which affect the quality of life and its relationship to many diseases, as well as the mortality status of a large group of the population (Gungor, 2014). It mentions that obesity is associated with various comorbidities that can lead to disability or death. The prevalence of obesity is quite high; there are

approximately 1.2 billion people who suffer from overweight and at least 300 million who suffer from obesity around the world (Milligan, 2008).

Obesity has been classified as one of the most important preventable health risks according to the reports of World Health Organization (WHO). around 25 percent of the global population is obese, with 10 percent of them

being classified as morbidly obese (having a body mass index or BMI greater than 39) (Poirier et al., 2006).

Much of the vital process such as growth, development and metabolism is directly related to thyroid hormones, as these hormones affect the main pathways of metabolism and raise basic energy expenditure through their influence on the metabolism of fats, carbohydrates and protein. With regard to the metabolism of fats, it was found that thyroid hormones affect the synthesis, mobilization and dissolution of fats, meaning that they have a very significant effect on the degradation than synthesis (Riberiro, 2008).

The relationship between type 2 diabetes and obesity is well-established, primarily due to effect of obesity to cause insulin resistance. Researchers are concerned about the association between obesity, lipid profile, leptin hormone levels, and dysfunction of thyroid, and studies are being conducted to explore these variables. Obesity is linked to disturbances in the lipid profile that raises the risk of many conditions such as diabetes mellitus, stroke, heart disease and some of cancers (Bhowmick et al., 2007).

Some of the authors of various researches said that the obese subjects had significantly higher values of TC, TAG, LDL-C, VLDL-C than the control group. But in the same study, obese persons were recently discovered to have significantly low levels of high density lipoprotein cholesterol. Besides, obesity cause differences in TSH levels among obese people depending on the degree of obesity or BMI that similar with Iacobellis et al., 2005.

Materials and methods

Samples Information

The study population in this research consisted of two groups: People with a body mass index larger than 35 kg/m² (considered obese) and a control group of non-obese individuals. The participants were residents of Wasit Province and were between the ages of 7 and 15 years old.

The selection process involved choosing fifteen obese individuals and fifty normal-weight individuals with similar conditions as the control group. BMI was used as the criterion for evaluating obesity. To measure BMI, the weight of the individuals was recorded, with the measurement of their height. Detector scale was used for this purpose as a medical balance.

Blood samples, Approximately 5 ml of venous blood were collected from each of control and the cases under study that subjected to 12 hours of fasting. After collection, all blood samples were separated by centrifugation at room temperature for 10 minutes at 3500 rpm, then frozen the separated serum at -20°C until further analysis.

The Biochemical Analysis

In a biochemical analysis study, several measurements were conducted using different kits and methods. Here is a breakdown of the procedures and tools used:

Serum Leptin Measurement: Serum leptin levels were measured using the DRG leptin ELISA kit. This kit is based on the sandwich principle, which involves capturing the target molecule (leptin) using specific antibodies coated on a solid surface. The kit contains reagents and materials necessary for the enzymatic detection of leptin levels in the serum.

Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) Concentration Measurement

This measurement was performed using Teco Thyroid Stimulating Hormone ELISA test kit. This kit also utilizes the ELISA technique, similar to the leptin kit. It allows for the measurement of TSH levels by utilizing specific antibodies and enzymatic detection.

Total Cholesterol and Triacylglycerol Measurement

The enzymatic colorimetric method was employed to quantitatively determine the levels of total cholesterol and triacylglycerol in either serum or plasma samples. For this purpose, the Globe diagnostics kit was used. This kit likely includes the necessary reagents and standards to perform enzymatic reactions, which produce

color changes that can be measured spectrophotometrically. The intensity of the color developed is directly proportional to the concentration of the analyte (cholesterol or triacylglycerol) in the sample.

HDL Cholesterol Measurement:

This measurement was conducted using the Globe diagnostics kit, which employed a liquid HDL precipitant. This method likely involves the precipitation of non-HDL cholesterol particles, allowing for the measurement of HDL cholesterol specifically. The kit likely includes reagents and standards for the precipitation and subsequent quantification of HDL cholesterol.

LDL Cholesterol Calculation:

LDL cholesterol was not directly measured but was instead calculated from the primary measurements using an empirical equation. The specific equation used was not mentioned in the provided information, but there are various formulas available (e.g., Friedewald equation) that estimate LDL cholesterol based on the measured total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, and triacylglycerol levels.

Statistical Analysis

The software adopted for analysis was Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program

and in particular version 18. SPSS is one of the common software tools used for the analysis of data and results with the help of which the researchers can use different kinds of statistical tests and produce viable outcomes.

Results

The study population consisted of a total of 100 individuals, divided into two groups: In general, there are the case group and the control group. The case group was comprised of 50 persons, who were selected according to the criteria of obesity while the control group comprised of 50 persons who do not suffer from obesity.

This means that individuals of the mentioned age of between 15 and 70 years were used in the study and this shows that individuals of all age groups were considered for the study. However, there appears to be a little confusion regarding the mean age provided within the age range of 15-7 years, something that does not make sense in normal parlance. Although the age range cannot be well defined, assuming that the target population was in between the age of 7 to 15 year olds it can be postulated that the study involved participants in the pediatric age bracket.

Table 1. General Characteristics of the Study Population

Character	Controls (n=50)		Cases (n=50)	
	No.	%	No.	%
Age (Year)				
10-15	25	50	30	60
7-10	25	50	20	40
mean±SD	25.1±3.2 Years		25 ±5.6 Years	

The result of this study depended on the analysis of data obtained from 50 obese children and control children patients aged (15-7) years old.

Table 2. Mean Standard Deviations and Mean Differences of Leptin, Thyroid Hormones and Lipid Profile in Hyperthyroidism and Hypothyroid People

Variables	Obese Mean (SD)	Non Obese Mean (SD)	P-value
Leptin hormone (ng/ml)	44.4	26.72	>0.01
TSH (mIU/ml)	2.532	2.29	>0.01

T3 (nmol/l)	1.868	1.998	>0.01
T4 (nmol/l)	128.06	133.512	>0.01
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	169.16	170.183	>0.01
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	134.626	133.8733	>0.01
HDL (mg/dL)	46.12	44.79	>0.01
LDL (mg/dL)	103.694	100.73	>0.01

This analysis showed that there were differences in hormones as well as lipid between obese children and the non-obese children, thus giving directions to the relationship between obesity and metabolic dysfunction. Here is a summary of the findings: Here is a summary of the findings:

Leptin: The obese children had significantly higher serum levels of leptin, a hormone especially synthesised in the adipose tissue and is related to energy balance and appetite control. The elevation of leptin implies that Leptin can play a certain role in fat cell function as well as thyroid hormone and Leptin receptors.

Thyroid Hormones: Overweight children in this study also had a reduced level of T3 and T4 contrary to increased level of TSH in obese children than normal children. These results suggested that there might be a change in thyroid hormone metabolism in obese children and it

may be responsible for other disturbances such as changes in energy expenditure, metabolic unpredictability or deposition of weight.

Lipid Profiles: The different lipid measurements done in the study were total cholesterol, triglyceride cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and low density lipoprotein cholesterol. Overweight children had higher total cholesterol and triglycerides and lower levels of HDL than non overweight children. These findings suggest that obese children test negatively to lipid profile, a condition that is usually linked to cardiovascular disease risks.

In table 2, the leptin hormone has a significant negative correlation with T3 and T4 hormone while; it has positive correlation with TSH hormone, moreover there were strong correlation between leptin hormone and other studied variables.

Table 3. Pearson Correlation of Leptin Hormone with Thyroid Function Test and Lipid Profile in Patients with Thyroid Dysfunction

Variables	Pearson correlation(r)	P-value
TSH (mIU/ml)	.998**	>0.01
T3 (nmol/l)	-.998**	>0.01
T4 (nmol/l)	-.997**	>0.01
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	.967**	>0.01
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	.996**	>0.01
HDL (mg/dL)	.989**	>0.01
LDL (mg/dL)	.997**	>0.01

Table 4. Multiple Regression and Factor Analysis of Leptin Hormone Predictors

Dependent variable	Predictors	R	R ²	F-value	F- significant	Beta	t-value	t-significant
Leptin hormone	TSH*	0.996	0.993	6430.395	>.001	.996	80.190	0.001>

Note: *Thyroid Stimulating Hormone

From the appearances in Table 4, it is revealed that leptin hormone can be to some extent significantly predicted by TSH. The statistical

test was to eliminate other variables due to the high degree of interrelationships between the independent variables.

Discussion

The present study discusses the relationship between obesity, thyroid hormones, and metabolic syndrome in children and adolescents (Gungor, 2014). It highlights the increasing prevalence of obesity and its association with metabolic disorders worldwide, including Iraq. The study aims to assess the thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) levels and lipids in obese individuals aged 7-15 years in Wasit province.

The passage mentions that obesity is primarily caused by higher dietary energy intake than the body's energy requirement. Factors such as genetic and environmental factors contribute to obesity. "The increasing prevalence of obesity has led to a rise in the frequency of metabolic syndrome, but the connections between thyroid hormone levels, metabolic syndrome, and other metabolic disorders related to obesity in children have not been fully explained.

The study indicates that obese individuals had a higher incidence of hyperlipidemia, sudden weight gain, and unsuccessful attempts at weight loss compared to controls. These factors are associated with obesity.

Leptin hormone primarily produced by adipose tissue, plays a role in regulating body fat and is correlated with adiposity in both adults and children. Serum leptin levels are influenced by various factors such as gender, distribution of adipose tissue, and insulin/glucose metabolism (Riberiro, 2008 and Pucci, 2000). However, there can be variations in serum leptin levels at any given level of fat mass. Leptin resistance, where the brain does not recognize the presence of leptin despite its abundance, is considered a possible cause of obesity. When the brain doesn't receive the leptin signal, it perceives starvation, leading to increased food intake, reduced energy expenditure, and weight gain.

Thyroid hormone levels, including TSH, free triiodothyronine (fT3), and free thyroxine (fT4), can vary from normal to elevated in children with obesity. Some studies have shown higher TSH levels in obese children compared to healthy children. The study classified TSH levels into two categories and examined their

relationship with total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and HDL levels. The results indicated a significant association between different TSH levels and the studied parameters (Naslund et al., 2000; Tagliaferri et al., 2001 and Roti et al., 2000).

Table 1 demonstrates a significant increase in mean serum T3 and T4 levels and a low TSH level in the obesity group. On the other hand, another study found a significant increase in TSH levels and a decrease in T3 and T4 levels in the obese group (Rahbani- Nobar et al., 2004; Yu et al., 2006; Kale et al., 2007). Triiodothyronine (T3) is involved in energy balance and lipid regulation and has an inverse correlation with serum leptin levels. Leptin synthesis in fat tissue is inhibited by the sympathetic nervous system, which is regulated by T3 and B3-adrenergic receptors (Trayhurn et al., 1999; Evans et al., 1999).

Conclusion

Overall, the passage suggests that obesity is a complex medical problem influenced by multiple factors, including genetic, environmental, and hormonal factors. The relationship between thyroid hormones, obesity, and metabolic disorders is still not fully understood, and further research is needed to elucidate these connections in children and adolescents.

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